

Prediction and Categorization Of COVID-19 Related Dermatological Manifestations Using Machine Learning

Dr. Shubhangi DC¹, Dr. M.A Waheed², Nameera Simran³, Dr. Basavaraj Gadgay⁴

¹Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, VTU Centre for PG Studies, Kalaburagi, Karnataka, drshubhangipatil1972@gmail.com

²Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, VTU Centre for PG Studies, Kalaburagi, Karnataka, dr.mawaheed@gmail.com

³Student, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, VTU Centre for PG Studies, Kalaburagi, Karnataka, nameerasimran22@gmail.com

⁴Regional Director, VTU Regional Office, Kalaburagi, Karnataka, baswaraj_gadgay@vtu.ac.in

ABSTRACT

COVID-19 is global epidemic instigated because of "severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus 2". Fever, cough, tiredness, dyspnea, and hyposmia/ hyposmia are all common signs. Dermatological indications have become more common in recent months among the extrapulmonary indicators associated with COVID-19. Our group proposed a taxonomy based on the polymorphic character of COVID-19-related cutaneous symptoms, which includes the following six primary clinical patterns: Urticarial rash, confluent erythematous / maculopapular / morbilliform rash, papulovesicular exanthem, chilblain-like acral, livedo reticularis / racemosa-like, purpuric "vasculitic" patterns. To offer an evaluation of possible pathophysiological routes of COVID-19-related cutaneous symptoms, this research focuses upon that clinical features & therapeutic treatment of every category. Machine learning algorithms such as SVM, RF, DT, KNN, LR, and NB are used in the analysis.

Keywords—COVID-19 erythematous/maculopapular/morbilliform

I. INTRODUCTION

An outbreak of acute pulmonary disorder corona virus 2 (SARS-CoV2), which causes COVID-19, has reached pandemic proportions. Even though fever & respiratory ailments like coughing and breathlessness are among most typical symptoms of a COVID-19 infection, other manifestations like arranging pneumonia & decreased lung function, & drug reactions as well as adverse effects, are becoming increasingly important as knowledge about the disease's pathophysiology & instinctual historiography grows. [1-4]. Skin lesions have recently been identified as possible COVID-19 symptoms. Erythematous rash, urticaria, livedo reticularis, vesicular lesions, and chilblain-like lesions have all been documented [5-12]. However, there is a lack of information on the prevalence and histology of COVID-19-related skin lesions, as well as the clinical, analytical, and radiographic results. The goal of our project is determining prevalence, clinical aspects, and histopathological findings of COVID-19-related cutaneous manifestations, as well as their link to other clinical-epidemiological features of COVID-19. The six groups are as follows:

We examined skin of 3 people with severe COVID19 and a purpuric rash on their skin. C5b9 and C4d deposition was seen in both severely damaged and normal-appearing skin, indicating a thrombogenic vasculopathy. Colocalization of COVID19 spike glycoproteins with C4d & C5b9 was seen in alveolar septa as well as cutaneous microvasculature of 2 of patients investigated. They came to the conclusion that at least a subgroup of individuals with long-term, severe COVID19 may have a type of catastrophic microvascular damage syndrome caused by complement activation and a procoagulant condition. As a result of circulating immune complexes damaging the tiny arteries of dermis, activation of complement pathways, & procoagulant milieu, there is a potential causal connection with COVID19 infection. Hypoxemia in the tissues could potentially be a factor. Some of the forms of COVID19-induced vasculitis include acrovasculitis and acroecrosis..

COVID19 infection is related with infectious and/or allergic skin lesions. The potential absence of a "herald patch" is a clinical characteristic of Papulosquamous rashes and pityriasis rosea presentation in COVID19 infection.

According to Sanchez et al. 8, most COVID19 patients have high levels of proinflammatory cytokines & infection-related indicators, and skin symptoms may represent the body's immunological response to the virus. The absence of the early herald patch distinguished the authors' rashes from classical pityriasis rosea. A similar situation was reported in which no herald patch could be found. As a result, this unusual type is now known as paraviral dermatosis, and clinicians must be conscious of this new clinical connection.

It is possible that COVID19 infectious rash are related to measles because of their comparable clinical features. According to Hunt & Koziatek, one 20year-old patient showed a generalized measles-like rash from across trunk and limbs but not on the face, suggesting that patient exhibited COVID19 infection. 10 Researchers found the rashes to be patchypapular that form, with pain however no pruritis, indicating that they were consistent with those of a viral exanthem. Avellana et al. 11 found measles-like rashes in 32year-old COVID19 patient on the sixth day following the onset of the illness, along with the normal symptoms of fever, chronic cough, myalgia, and tiredness. A frequent occurrence are petechial and maculopapular eruptions. On the fourth day, the rashes faded and peeling began. Amatore et al. 12 described the "febrile" rash of COVID19 infection in 39year-old patient. Erythematous and edematous papules & round-shaped plaques on the upper limbs, chest, neck, abdomen, and palms were the hallmarks of rashes; however, the face and mucous membranes were not affected. Lymphocyte exocytosis, perivascular lymphocytic infiltrates with no eosinophils, papillary dermal edoema, including single basal sites of dyskeratotic infiltration were all seen in the affected area in same way as in viral exanthems. The dermatologic results in our instance are quite similar.

Papulovesicular rashes appear when the body temperature is increased, resulting in profuse sweating. Anatomical distributions of such rash might vary widely from those of classic heat itch (miliaria rubra) presentation. 9 percent of those with cutaneous symptoms had vesicular eruptions caused by COVID19 infection, as per Casas et al. 9's generally recognized findings. Furthermore, the authors claim that truncal localization is the most common. Marzano A.V. et.al¹³ reported in 22 COVID19 infected patients who developed papulovesicular eruptions comparable to chickenpox. Our findings support the following clinical symptoms of COVID19 infection-related skin eruption.

The aetiology might be dual, depending on where it comes from. Urticarial eruptions, upon 1 arm, might be predecessor to development of COVID19 or occurring concurrently early signs. Urticaria, basically, is a clinical symptom of CADR that frequently arises as a result of drug intolerance. The acral configuration of the blisters in our case supports a viral aetiology.

Drug rashes are caused by individual individuals' intolerance to drugs and are not linked to COVID19 infection. Antibacterial agents are among the most prevalent causes of bacterial infection. CADR with antiviral, antimicrobial, as well as other drugs is not ruled out based on previous clinical instances of COVID19 disease skin rashes.

Called as "bilateral axillary purple rash," according to Spanish experts, represents a distinct skin group symptoms of COVID19. 9 Though, its distinctive look and placement, in our judgement, are most likely CADR manifestations. During course of illness whilst also on medicine, our patient's rash spread far beyond inguinal lines. The case series' flaws include the absence of histological study of skin lesions found as, in some instances, inability to examine patients at onset of symptoms. Despite our suspicions of viral origin in three cases, CADR could not be ruled out. The aforementioned constraints will likely become less relevant when medicinal amenities are accessible for patients suffering COVID19 disease.

Finally, it's worth noting that the importance of the stated dermatological signs are currently debated. Infected individuals with COVID19 may benefit from their presence in the diagnosis, treatment, or prognosis. However, although we remain taking care of our patient, we should keep an eye out for any new developments & communicate them with our colleagues.

II. RELATED WORK

In this case, Huang C [1] Hospitals in Wuhan, China, received all patients who may have had 2019-nCoV. Patients infected with 2019-nCoV were studied using actual RT-PCR & next sequencing, respectively. The WHO & ISAREIC published data collecting forms for electronic medical records. Patients or members of their families

were also interviewed to get epidemiological & symptomatic data. To determine whether or not ICU admission was necessary, the outcomes of ICU patients and those that did not were evaluated.

AV Marzano [2] CoronaVirus Disease19 (COVID19), The newly discovered SARSCoV2 virus has spread fast so over globe. COVID19's clinical range is expanding & new symptoms are appearing even as number of patients increases exponentially all across globe. The prevalence of various cutaneous symptoms in COVID19 individuals has been documented in numerous papers. To give a high-level review of the COVID19-related cutaneous lesions. Up until April 30, 2020, PubMed, Scopus, & Web of Science indexes were searched for relevant material. This narrative review summarizes the current evidence on clinicopathological features of COVID19-related cutaneous symptoms.

Infection with SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19): French case & thorough literature review [3]. COVID-related cutaneous symptoms have increased in recent years, according to J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol. The purpose of this research was to conduct a systematic evaluation of literature and examine experience of a French referral center. COVID19 patients admitted at Cochin Hospital during March 16th & April 27th 2020 had their skin conditions evaluated. The hospital found 759 instances with moderate-to-severe COVID-19.

COVID-19 cutaneous symptoms are classified. Galván Casas C, Català A, Carretero Hernández G, Rodríguez-Jiménez P, Fernández-Nieto D, Rodríguez-Villa Lario A, et al[4]: 375 patients in a quick prospective countrywide consensus study in Spain. The cutaneous symptoms of COVID-19 illness are poorly understood, according to Br J Dermatol. 2020 Jul;183(1):71-7. A countrywide imaging & clinical data gathering survey was conducted. 5 clinical patterns were defined to use a consensus.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The collection of data is first step in the procedure. Processing of Data Preprocessing comprises cleaning and reducing information before it is transformed..

The objective is to create a portal to receive images and run it by an algorithm to identify the type of skin disease. The first step is collecting a large number of images(10,000+) for different types of skin diseases. After that research into the medical field to study these images and based on that developing & fine-tuning algorithm to produce more and more accuracy. Developing a user-friendly portal where the user can upload images and get the result after processing.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Figure 1: System Architecture

IV. METHODOLOGY

The procedure includes 4 steps

- 1) Dataset Collecting,
 - 2) Dataset Preprocess,
 - 3) Extracting of Feature, and
 - 4) Classifying.
- a. Data Collection: Every picture that go into program are in RGB color model.
- b. Data Preprocessing. Into our research, data handling follows the below steps .

Step1: Accept and change contrast & brightness of input RGB pictures

Step2: Converting RGB pictures in Grayscale pictures.

Step 3: Using a median filter, remove the noise from each R, G, and B color channel. It is especially good at eliminating noises like salt and pepper. After sorting the neighboring pixel values numerically, pixel being examined is substituted by median value of all other pixel values as in pattern. To remove noise without sacrificing picture clarity, use median filter.

$$f(x, y) = \text{median}_{(u,v) \in K_{xy}} \{g(u, v)\}$$

Here K_{xy} responds as coordinated sets focused upon point (x,y) , median indicates window's median value inside rectangle sub-image window..

c. Feature Extraction. GLCM is employed for feature selecting in this experiment. It involves statistical texture examination. 2nd-order statistical texture investigation approach. This method calculates statistical info with every grayscale image pixel's neighbour.

$$\text{CON} = \sum \sum (i - j)^2 P(i - j)$$

$$\text{ENT} = - \sum \sum P(i - j) \log [P(i, j)]$$

$$\text{COR} = \frac{\sum \sum ijP(i-j) - \mu_x \mu_y}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

d. Classification procedure begins whenever GLCM features have been calculated from pictures. Below are stages involved in categorization procedure.,

- 1) Choosing system,
- 2) Train the model,
- 3) Evaluating model,
- 4) Tuning constraints,
- 5) Predicting result. Following classifying systems have been utilised, SVM, KNN, DT & Random forest algorithms.

Support Vector Machine (SVM). It's an learning algorithm that is supervised. Such approach uses kernel function to transform complicated data. To create a clear prediction, it optimises the separation between the classes. The multiclass SVM approach is employed in this case. The multiclass problem is broken down into binary classes using this approach. The algorithm then runs for each binary pair and makes a forecast.

SVM Algorithm Pseudo Code:

Candsv={nearest pair from opposite classes}

Whilst there's violating points do

Finding violator

Candsv=U candsv

S

Violator

If $\alpha p < 0$ because of adding c to S then

Candsv=candsv\p

Repeating untill every point is pruned

Endif
 End while

K-nearest neighbor (KNN). It's an method of supervised learning. Each sample was categorised according to its surrounding samples using this procedure. As a result, if an unknown sample needs to be categorised, it can be classified by its neighbouring samples. When a classifier is given a training dataset and an unknown sample, When a sample is unknown, this algorithm calculates distance among unidentified sample as well as all previously collected datasets. Unknown samples are compared to that same training set with lowest value to determine their distance from each other. To categorise an unknown sample, the performance of KNN is mostly determined by the value of K, the number of nearest neighbours. When k is really tiny, the classification is poor. However, the biggest amount of k yields the best classification

Nearest-Neighbor($D[1 \dots n, 1 \dots n], s$)

//Input: A $n \times n$ distance matrix $D[1 \dots n, 1 \dots n]$ & index
 s of the city starting.

//Output: List Path of vertices containing tour is
 obtained.

for $i \leftarrow 1$ to n do Visited[i] $\leftarrow$ *false*

Initialize list Path with s

Visited[s] $\leftarrow$ *true*

Current $\leftarrow$ s

to n do

Find low element into row current & not marked column j having element

Current $\leftarrow$ j

Visited[j] $\leftarrow$ *true*

Add j to ending of list Path

Add s to ending of list Path

return Path

for $i \leftarrow 2$

V. IMPLEMENTATION

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluating Indicator

Several performance factors are used to assess the performance of skin disease image identification. Proportion of accurate prediction outcomes in overall sample: accuracy (ACC) ; true positive rate (TPR), commonly called by sensitivity & Recall (R) ; true negative rate (TNR), sometimes called as specificity shows that real disease-free is properly determined to be disease-free.

$$\text{Accuracy Acc} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FN+FP}$$

$$\text{Sensitivity or TPR} = TP / (TP + FN)$$

$$\text{Specificity or TNR} = TN / (FP + TN)$$

Achieved results:

Figure 2: Menu

The fig 2 shows the steps involved in prediction of covid related dermatological manifestations.

Figure 3: Skin Image

The above figure shows the skin image as input to identify manifestation.

Figure 4:Preprocessing

The figure 4 shows the preprocessing of the image

Figure 5: Segmentation

The fig describes the segmentation of original image into gray scale image and then into threshold image

Figure 6: Study of manifestation in population

The graph for increasing no of patients according to the respective disease or manifestation is shown in above figure

Table1:Results

Disease	Sensitivity	Specificity
Cutaneous Vasculatides	90.66%	85.65%
Papulosquamous rashes , pityriasis rosea	93,22%	92.55%
Measles	96.77%	89.53%
Papulovesicular rashes	87.94%	94.02%
Utricular rashes	87.37%	89.12%
CADR	95.74%	94.39%

The above table shows the sensitivity and specificity obtained for the manifestations

VI. CONCLUSION

This technology, which we may utilise like efficient, cost efficient resolution for Covid-19 associated skin disease diagnosis using AI system, is offered for resolving complexities which are produced by encounters experienced by dermatologists in quickly recognising various skin disorders. Two noise reduction technologies were tested after first applying modifications to reduce the noise. In order to increase computation efficiency, There was a comparison of noise reduction with the Gaussian filter with the median filter, and four color spaces for skin lesion identification & extraction of features using median filter.

COVID-19-associated skin lesions need more investigation into the histopathological elements of disease, including viral particles and genetic material, and the immunologic pattern.

REFERENCES

- [1] Huang C, Wang Y, Li X, Ren L, Zhao J, Hu Y, et al. Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China. *Lancet*. 2020 Feb;395(10223):497–506.
- [2] Marzano AV, Cassano N, Genovese G, Moltrasio C, Vena GA. Cutaneous manifestations in patients with COVID-19: a preliminary review of an emerging issue. *Br J Dermatol*. 2020 Sep;183(3):431–42.
- [3] Matar S, Oulès B, Sohier P, Chosidow O, Beylot-Barry M, Dupin N, et al. Cutaneous manifestations in SARS-CoV-2 infection (COVID-19): a French experience and a systematic review of the literature. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2020 Jun;jdv.16775.
- [4] Galván Casas C, Català A, Carretero Hernández G, Rodríguez-Jiménez P, Fernández-Nieto D, Rodríguez-Villa Lario A, et al. Classification of the cutaneous manifestations of COVID-19: a rapid prospective nationwide consensus study in Spain with 375 cases. *Br J Dermatol*. 2020 Jul;183(1):71–7.
- [5] Potekaev NN, Zhukova OV, Protsenko DN, Demina OM, Khlystova EA, Bogin V. Clinical characteristics of dermatologic manifestations of COVID-19 infection: case series of 15 patients, review of literature, and proposed etiological classification. *Int J Dermatol*. 2020 Aug;59(8):1000–9.
- [6] Gisoni P, Piaserico S, Bordin C, Alaibac M, Girolomoni G, Naldi L. Cutaneous manifestations of SARS-CoV-2 infection: a clinical update [online ahead of print]. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2020 Jun;jdv.16774.
- [7] Imbalzano E, Casciaro M, Quartuccio S, Minciullo PL, Cascio A, Calapai G, et al. Association between urticaria and virus infections: A systematic review. *Allergy Asthma Proc*. 2016 Jan-Feb;37(1):18–22.
- [8] Yong SB, Yeh WC, Wu HJ, Chen HH, Huang JY, Chang TM, et al. Impact of mycoplasma pneumonia infection on urticaria: A nationwide, population-based retrospective cohort study in Taiwan. *PLoS One*. 2019 Dec;14(12):e0226759.
- [9] Recalcati S. Cutaneous manifestations in COVID-19: a first perspective. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2020 May;34(5):e212–3.
- [10] Freeman EE, McMahon DE, Lipoff JB, Rosenbach M, Kovarik C, Desai SR, et al. The spectrum of COVID-19-associated dermatologic manifestations: an international registry of 716 patients from 31 countries.